

**ASSESSMENT OF JOB STRESS AND ITS IMPACT ON WORK-LIFE BALANCE
AND PROFESSIONAL COMMITMENT - A CASE STUDY**

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Abstract

Stress is the major problem in today's turmoil working environment. Stress is main source of decreasing employees' commitment towards their job. The present study is conducted to examine the impact of job stress on work-life balance and professional commitment among Grama Ward Secretariats Employees of Tadepalli, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh. The data has been collected from 70 employees of Grama Ward Secretariats employees of Guntur District.

Keywords: Grama Ward Secretariats, Job Stress, Professional Commitment, Tadepalli, Work-Life Balance

1. Introduction

Present life is full of hassles, deadlines, frustrations, and stress. In the fast changing world of today, no one is free from stress and no profession is stress free. Modern life is full of stress. As organizations become more complex the potential for and amount of stress increases. Urbanization, industrialization and raise in scale of operations in the society are causing rising stress. In 1970 the American Journalist and sociologist Alvin Toffler predicted that the rate of change in modern civilization would accelerate to such a degree that enormous number of people would experience shattering stress and disorientation. Toffler described this condition as "Future Shock". Many civilizations are feeling the impact of global change. The effects of change reach into every gap of life putting people more and more under pressure. Human life evolution is falling behind developments in technology and lifestyle. Physiological and Psychological stress emerges as a result of increasing deficit between daily demands and coping resources.

Stress can be defined as a state of worry or mental health issue caused by a difficult situation. Stress has been conceptualized in the following ways (i) it is a feeling or emotional or physical tension that comes from any event or thought that makes you feel frustrated, angry, depression (ii) it is a normal reaction the body has when changes occur, resulting in physical, emotional and intellectual responses (iii) as interaction outcome of the external demand and internal resources and (iv) as personal response to a certain variation in the environment. Moreover, it is umbrella term for a comprehensive catalogue of words that include anxiety, tension, conflict,

pressure strain, panic, depression, burnout, etc. Generally, it is a demand on the body, physically or mentally, that exceeds the person's ability to cope. There are various causes of job stress like lack of control, increased responsibility, performance, uncertainty about work roles, poor communication, lack of support, poor working conditions, rotating shifts, job insecurity, high demand for performance, technology, workplace culture, personal and family problems and job stress and women.

There are various factors involved of Grama Ward Secretariats Employees like reward and recognition, time constraints, departmental influence, professional identity, client interaction, etc.

Professional Commitment is ahead of a commitment for an organization and implies the individual's perspective towards their professional and the motivation that they have to stay in their job with readiness to strive and uphold the morals and goals of the profession. A member of an organization's psychology regarding his or her relationship to the company they work for is described as having a professional commitment. Whether an employee will stay with the company for a longer amount of time and put their all into attaining the company's goal depends critically on the professional commitment. It can categorize into three components

1. Affective commitment
2. Continuance commitment
3. Normative commitment

Job Stress directly affects the life of Grama Ward Secretariats employees; it makes their work more difficult, so it adversely affects the psychological and physical health of the employees. Through work-life imbalance employees are mentally disturbed because they deal directly general public regarding government schemes. The Grama Ward Secretariats occupation is one of the most stressful jobs. Employees work patters are changing because of their field work, collect data directly from public, etc., Sometimes there is ample of work stress on employees so that they have to increase their working hours especially when they are in field work, they are not also able to spend their quality time with their family and it also affects their way of life habits. The need for work-life balance emerges as a response to the struggle between personal and professional which occurs when the personal role requirements are mismatched with the organizational roles and vice versa (Ruppner Leah, 2013).

2. Related Works

Misbah et. Al. (2015) experienced the relation between job stress and organizational commitment in banking sector. The research found that there is negative and insignificant relation among respective variables. **Cristiana Catalina Circei (2012)** studied Occupational stress and organizational commitment in Romanian public organizations. The sample collected 102 employees from Romanian public organization and found negative relation found in between stress and commitment. **Yaghoubi et al. (2008)** also explained that there is not a significant relationship between continuance commitment and job stress. **Somers (2009)** found no significant relationship between job stress and continuance commitment. **Dywili M (2015)**

examined the role of occupational stress as a possible cause of the intentions to quit among the employees of Nkonkobe municipality in Alice and Fort Beaufort, Eastern Cape. **Rajeshwaran and Aktharsha (2017)**, made an examination on impact of different types of stress on organizational commitment and furthermore “impact of organizational commitment on job performance and job satisfaction”. Results established that the “personality related stress, family related stress, burn out related stress and subordinate related stress” are the main indicators of organizational commitment. It was also found that job performance is by and just regulated by continuance commitment where as job satisfaction is impacted by normative commitment. It shows that it would be difficult for staff to leave the organization, if there could be no other alternatives for them to think about leaving and also, staying with the organization perceives like an obligation as much as of desire. It also implies that job satisfaction can be enjoyed when staff is obliged and loyal towards their organizations. It is also recommended that staff should cultivate “affective and normative commitment” to get satisfied with job for their own advantages. **Ali et al. (2018)** performed a research on manufacturing sector in Peshawar to determine relationship among “job satisfaction, organizational commitment and desire of personnel to turnover”. Their survey affirmed that job satisfaction is empathically connected to organizational commitment, while turnover desire found insignificant is negative related with “job satisfaction as well as organizational commitment”. **Mrs. RadhaDamleDr.Sharad L. Joshi (2012)** attempted to investigate occupational stress encountered by central government employees, coping strategies adopted by them and their relation with employee performance. **Ahmad, Bharadwaj, and Narula (1985)** assess stress levels among 30 executives from both the public and private sector, using an ORS scale to measure ten dimensions of role stress-role isolation, role ambiguity, and self-role distance. The authors also establish the insignificant effect of several background factors, like age, education level, income, marital status, and work experience. **U. Syed Aktharsha, A. Selvamathi (2019)**, job stress factors namely limits of authority on job, increases over all job satisfaction, on the other hand, job stress factors viz., Lack of knowledge of specific procedures and conflicts in order erodes overall job satisfaction. Moreover, burnout factors viz., hard work, handling problems effectively and positively influencing other’s people’s life significantly leads to increased job satisfaction and some of the burnout factors viz., feeling of being used up, burnout from work, working with people directly causing stress, absence of public welfare, and lesser sense of accomplishment erodes overall job satisfaction of government employees. **Oward (1980)** studied managers from 12 major Canadian companies and found that stress originate in many ways like; poor management, lack of authority or blurred organizational relationships, promotion and recognition concerns, basis business problems, company politics, personal problems, work volumes, unfamiliarity, and miscellaneous which included problems concerning personal shortcomings and the price paid for being a perfectionist. Fear of decision making was also a concern, especially when it involved the careers of others. **Fenwick Rudy & Tausig Mark (2001)**, examined the casual correlation between alternate work schedules and perceived work-life balance. It was revealed that a higher degree of schedule management and schedule control improves work-life balance. **Ojo Dare et al (2015)**, extensively researched the multiple work-life balance initiative in the banking industry. The result from the study shows that job-related attitude and leave initiative were not

significantly correlated with each other. **Mullen Kathleen (2015)**, analyzed the connection between work-life balance significantly correlated with the demands of their work environment. **Akhilesh Gaurm Dr. R.C. Gupta and Dr. Gaurav Jaiswal (2021)**, found that work-life balanced positively affects the personal and professional life as well as the satisfaction level of a bank employees and work life balance shared a significant and positive relationship with job satisfaction and have moderate and positive nature with occupational stress.

3. Statement of the problem

There are so many antecedents of Professional Commitment and one of them is Job Stress, still understanding what influence job stress can have on provocation and professional commitment isn't complete and not stable. However, a huge quantum of exploration benefactions stated a negative influence of stress of job on the commitment of association, while other exploration benefactions have noted a positive influence of these factors. Several experimenters have contributed to the proposition of work stress, which has redounded in reducing workers' satisfaction towards the job & commitment towards their work. The gap in the exploration makes it important to understand if Job Stress has a positive or negative impact on incitement & PC of workers which is a conflict gap.

During this modern world also these elements are still affecting the employees working in the public and private sectors. Zeal to study the above said factors researchers have chosen Grama Ward Secretariats Employees of Tadepalli, Guntur District of Andhra Pradesh.

4. Research Design and Methodology

The research technique serves as the researcher's road map or itinerary for achieving the study's objectives. This work explains the research design that was applied to the study as well as the different methods and techniques used for data collection and analysis.

4.1. Research Design

The research design facilitates the acquisition of responses pertaining to the research questions and the testing or confirmation of the study's hypotheses. During this investigation, it actually served as a plan more than a guide. This was accomplished through a methodical process that included choosing the research technique, research method, sample size and procedure. The final phase outlined the data analysis strategy. Flick (2012) posits that the research design serves as a window into the nature of the study and establishes its framework. The researchers evaluated stress and its impact on professional commitment in Grama Ward Secretariats employees of Tadepalli, Guntur district of Andhra Pradesh.

4.2 Objectives of the study:

1. To assess the job stress and its impact on professional commitment among Grama Ward Secretariats Employees of Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.
2. To know the demographic profile of the employees of Grama Ward Secretariats of Guntur District.
3. To study the factors related to job stress and its impact on professional commitment of employees of Grama Ward Secretariats of Guntur District.
4. To examine the impact of job stress on work-life balance of employees.

4.3 Study area and Target population

The present study is an attempt to study the assessment of job stress and its impact on professional commitment. Based on the literature review the researcher has identified the following research gap. Even though several research studies have been conducted in various sectors in the areas of Job Stress and professional commitment throughout the world, the research on Grama Ward Secretariats Employees Stress and professional commitment is not carried out extensively with reference to India and particularly to Andhra Pradesh and more particular among ward secretariat employees of Guntur District. Earlier studies conducted in the areas of VRO's, MRO's and Tahsildars job stress and job satisfaction with reference to Taluk members. Grama Ward Secretariat concept has been introduced recently in the state of Andhra Pradesh and no studies are available in the above said area. Hence the researchers have focused to study the Job Stress and its impact on Professional Commitment in Tadepalli Grama Ward.

4.4 Sampling technique

A convenience sampling technique has been used for this study which implies that where the employees are easily accessible to collect the first hand information from them.

4.5 Tools Employed

The objectives of the present study require those tools that measure the following dimensions

- Job stress
- Work-Life balance
- Professional Commitment

On a careful survey it finds that no single instrument would measure all three dimensions mentioned above, as a result taking into availability and suitability of the various instruments, the following three scales were identified.

- Job stress – Job Stress Measure
- Work-life – Likert's 5 point scale
- Professional Commitment – Likert's 5 point scale

4.6 Division of Research Instrument

Part I – Deals with Demographic variables

Part II – Deals with GWSE Stress Measure

Part III – Deals with Work-Life Events Scale

Part IV – Deals with Professional Commitment

4.7 Data collection method

Data has been collected from both primary and secondary sources.

A well structured questionnaire has been designed and distributed to the sample respondents in order to collect the primary data and magazines, Google search engine and journals, etc., were used to gather secondary data.

4.8 Analysis of data

Descriptive statistics was used to analyse the data. These are computed with the aid of the MS-Excel.

1. The scores were computed for the total sample according to the scorings given in the scales.

2. ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) was used to establish: if there is a significant difference exists between the levels of job stress towards professional commitment and work-life balance of GWSE.
3. Factor Analytical Approach (FAA), was used to define various dimensions of job stress. Mean and Standard Deviation techniques are applied to compute the factors effecting job stress and professional commitment of GWSE.
4. Regression analysis was used to know the relationship between Job Stress and Professional Commitment and work-life balance of the employees.

4.9 Hypotheses for the study

1. **H₀**: There is no significant impact of job stress on professional commitment among Grama Ward Secretariats Employees.
H_a: There is a significant impact of job stress on professional commitment among Grama Ward Secretariats Employees.
2. **H₀**: There is no significant impact of job stress on work-life balance on Employees.
H_a: There is a significant impact of job stress on work-life balance on Employees.

5. Limitations of the study

1. Due to time and money constraints the sampling Grama Wards were choosen in Tadepalli, Gurtur District of Andhra Pradesh.
2. The primary data was collected through a well structured questionnaire which will self reported by the respondents have its own limitation of subjectivity.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Frequency table for demographic parameters of survey responses

Demographic parameters	Frequency
Age	n (%)
25-30 years	12 (17.1)
31-35 years	13 (18.6)
35-40 years	25 (35.7)
41-45 years	20 (28.6)
Gender	
Male	31 (44.3)
Female	39 (55.7)
Marital status	
Married	60 (85.7)
Unmarried	10 (14.3)
Educational qualifications	
Ph.D.	3 (4.3)
PG	25 (35.7)
UG	42 (60.0)
Work Experience	
5-10 years	40 (57.1)
10-15 years	16 (22.9)
15-20 years	14 (20.3)

Chart 1 Frequency table for demographic parameters of survey responses

The provided data presents the demographic distribution of survey participants across various parameters: Age, Gender, Marital Status, Educational Qualifications, and Work Experience. The majority of participants fall within the age range of 35-40 years (35.7%), followed closely by those aged 41-45 years (28.6%). Younger participants, between 25-30 and 31-35 years, make up 17.1% and 18.6% of the sample, respectively. The gender distribution in the survey shows a relatively balanced representation, with females comprising a slightly higher percentage of respondents (55.7%) compared to males (44.3%). The overwhelming majority of participants are married (85.7%), indicating that this survey sample consists mainly of individuals in committed relationships. The educational background of the respondents is diverse, with a significant majority holding undergraduate degrees (60.0%). Postgraduates constitute 35.7% of the sample, while Ph.D. holders represent a smaller portion i.e., 4.3%.

A substantial portion of the participants has 5-10 years of work experience (57.1%). Participants with 10-15 years and 15-20 years of experience make up 22.9% and 20.3% of the sample, respectively. The descriptive analysis of job stress towards professional commitment and work-life balance has been presented in the following table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis of Job Stress towards Professional Commitment and Work-Life balance

Constructs	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Job Stress	3.827143	0.342168	70
Work-Life balance	4.07551	0.214419	70
Professional Commitment	4.059524	0.234049	70

Job Stress as control variable along with Professional Commitment and Work-Life balance of employees working in Grama Ward Secretariats in Guntur District shows the mean and SD 3.82 to 4.07 respectively. Least mean recorded by Job Stress (M = 3.827) and Work-Life balance Standard Deviation (SD = 0.214), followed by higher mean for Work-Life balance (M = 4.075) and Job Stress Standard Deviation (SD = 0.342). Correlation Analysis of Job Stress towards Professional Commitment and Work-Life balance has been presented in the subsequent table 3.

Table 3: Correlation Analysis

Constructs		1	2	3
Job Stress		1		
Work-Life balance	Pearson correlation (2-tailed)	0.084538	1	
Professional Commitment	Pearson correlation (2-tailed)	0.211777	0.108541	1

Table 3 presents correlation analysis that shows strength of association between the respective variables i.e., Job Stress, Work-Life balance and Professional Commitment. Pearson correlation was used as data were normally distributed. It shows positive significant relation ($r = 0.08$, $p < .05$) between Job Stress and Work-Life balance and ($r = 0.21$, $p < .05$) between Job Stress and Professional Commitment. As well as there is a positive and weak correlation ($r = 0.108$, $p < .05$) between Work-Life balance and Professional Commitment. The model summary with regard to impact of job stress on work-life balance and professional commitment has been portrayed in the succeeding table 4.

Table 4: Model summary showing impact of Job Stress on Work-Life balance and Professional Commitment

Constructs	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error	Change Statistics			
					R Square Change	df1	df2	Sif. F Change
Work-Life balance	0.084538	0.007147	-0.00745	0.343441	0.007	1	68	0.486
Professional Commitment	0.211777	0.044849	0.030803	0.336856	0.044	1	68	0.078

Predictors: (Constant), Stress

Dependent variable: Work-Life balance, Professional Commitment

The R-square value for work-life balance is 0.007, which means that job stress explains only 0.7% of the variance in work-life balance. The adjusted R-square value is negative. Whereas Professional Commitment predicted the results based on Job Stress of R-square change shows 0.044 i.e., 4.4% variance observed towards dependent factor. The adjusted R-square value is positive. The change statistics table shows that the R-square change value for professional commitment is statistically significant. Measuring fitness level of Job Stress on Professional Commitment and Work-Life balance by using ANOVA has been depicted in the next table 5.

Table 5: ANOVA measuring fitness level of Job Stress on Professional Commitment and Work-Life balance

	<i>df</i>	<i>Sum of Square</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Regression (WL)	1	0.057	0.057	0.489	0.486
Residual	68	8.020	0.117		
Total	69	8.078			
Regression (PC)	1	0.362	0.362	3.192	0.078
Residual	68	7.716	0.113		
Total	69	8.078			

Predictors: (Constant), Stress

Dependent Variables: Work-Life balance, Professional Commitment

The F-statistic for the regression analysis predicting work-life balance is 0.489, and the p-value is 0.486, which means it is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level of significance then the study cannot reject the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between job stress and work-life balance. The F-statistic for the regression analysis professional commitment is 3.192, and the p-value is 0.078, which means analysis is statistically significant at the 0.10 level of significance i.e., the study can reject the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between job stress and professional commitment. The mean square for the regression analysis predicting work-life balance is 0.057, and the mean square for the residual is 0.117, i.e., it explains very little of the variance in work-life balance (about 4%). Further it predicting professional commitment is 0.362, and the mean square for the residual is 0.113, i.e., it explains a moderate amount of the variance in professional commitment (about 32%). Respondents opinion towards their level of stress experienced in their present Job has been depicted in the following table 6.

Table 6: Respondents opinion towards their level of stress experienced in their present Job

Opinions	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)	Cumulative %
Low stress	1	1.42	1.42
Moderate stress	55	78.58	80
High stress	14	20	100
Total	70	100	100

Graph 2: Respondents opinion towards their level of stress experienced in their present Job

Chart 2 clearly states that only 1.42 % of the employees experienced low stress where as majority of the respondents (i.e., 79%) were moderately affected and the rest of the sample opined that they are experienced in a higher level. Respondent’s opinion towards their level of job stress experienced in their daily life was projected in the subsequent table 7.

Table 7: Respondents opinion towards their level of stress experienced in their daily life

Opinions	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Low stress	5	7.14
Moderate stress	48	68.57
High stress	17	24.28
Total	70	100

Chart 3: Respondents opinion towards their level of stress experienced in their daily life

Table 7 projects the opinions of the sample respondents towards their level of stress experienced in their daily life. Only 7.14% were affected in a lower manner and majority of the respondents i.e., 68.57% were moderately affected in their daily life due to because of job stress and the remaining 24.28% of the sample employees opined that they were highly affected.

6. Summary of Results

6.1 Demographic result reveals

- Most of the respondents are in the age group of 35-40 years.
- Majority of the respondents working in Grama Ward Secretariats are males.
- Around 42% of the respondents are under graduates (UG).
- The entiresample employee's are havingwork experience between 5-20 years in various fields.

6.2 Descriptive Analysis- Correlation and Regression Results

- The mean score for job stress is slightly above the midpoint of the scale. Hence, the respondents are experiencing moderate levels of job stress due to work overload, tight deadlines or difficult relationship with colleagues or supervisors.
- The mean score for work-life balance is above the midpoint of the scale. Hence, the respondents are generally satisfied with their work-life balance.
- The mean score for professional commitment is above the midpoint of the scale. Hence, the respondents are highly committed to their careers.

- Correlation analysis found that there is a complex relationship between job stress, work-life balance and professional commitment. While job stress is generally associated with lower levels of work-life balance, it is also associated with higher levels of professional commitment.
- Regression analysis found that the job stress is a significant predictor of professional commitment, but not of work-life balance.
- Professional commitment has a moderate amount of the variance but work-life balance has very little of the variance.

7. Recommendations

- Having a certain objective in mind facilitates prioritization. After the objectives are determined, they can be prioritized and worked towards in that order. As a result, work can be finished on schedule and logically. The capacity to prioritize objectives demonstrates a worker's forward-thinking and planning skills.
- The organization must develop and put into place a strong and efficient stress management system, as it was discovered to be deficient, in order to improve employee performance. Furthermore, the concerned authorities must implement an Employee Assistance Program, a proactive step that detects issues and takes action before they have an impact on employee's performance. It is well known that acknowledgment and praise have a positive impact. It is imperative that managers cultivate the practice of praising and acknowledging employees for their outstanding work by means of awards, merit systems, and other benefits or bonuses.
- Opportunities for growth that are well-defined can support workers' motivation and output. Their employees become de-motivated due to a lack of growth opportunities, which in turn impacts their performance. The authorities should also think about hiring more people for each branch. It will be easier to reduce the workload and number of hours worked if the number is increased from what it was when the research was done. Employees should be permitted to leave the office at a reasonable hour rather than being pushed to put in excessive overtime except when they are in field work.

8. Summary and Conclusion

The study found that job stress has a weak but positive relationship with work-life balance and a moderate positive relationship with professional commitment. It means that employees who are experienced in facing higher levels of job stress tend to report lower levels of work-life balance and higher levels of professional commitment. Overall, the findings of the study suggest that job stress is a complex phenomenon that has a variety of effects on employee well-being and productivity. AP Government should take necessary steps in-order to reduce job stress among the employees of Grama Ward Secretariats by providing adequate resources and extending their support which in-turn leadsto professional commitment by the employees.

9. Future Research Direction

The present study has been carried out among the employees of Grama Ward Secretariats Tadepalli, Guntur district of Andhra Pradesh towards Job Stress by considering some variables with regard to work-life balance and professional commitment. The study can be extended to other wards of Guntur district of Andhra Pradesh and a comparison can be made among the different wards of Guntur District as well as the other elements like job insecurity, boring work, changes to duties, tight deadlines etc., can be considered for further study. The research work can be extended to various districts of Andhra Pradesh and a comparison can be made towards Job Stress and its impact on professional commitment with regard to Grama Ward Secretariats.

10. Authors Contributions

The conceptualization of the work and the data analysis were greatly aided by the contributions of all authors. Additionally, authors made a significant contribution to the work's drafting and revision. Every author agrees to take responsibility for every element of the effort to guarantee that inquiries about the precision and integrity of any component of the work is duly examined and concluded. The final draft is approved for publication by all authors.

11. Conflict of Interest

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this paper.

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